

Skills 4 eosc

D6.4 Evaluation Report of the Fellowship Programme for (Aspiring) Data Professionals

Lead Partner:	TU Delft, Netherlands
Version:	1.0
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16535431
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.16535431

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is a report on the Skills4EOOSC Fellowship Programme for data professionals and is related to Task 6.4 of the Skills4EOOSC project; to establish a Fellowship Programme to support life-long learning and knowledge exchange. The Programme supported professional development within Open Science, research data management and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles through secondments lasting between 1-3 months at a host institution. Both aspiring and experienced data stewards or other data professionals could apply.

The report presents the development, administration, roll-out, and evaluation of the Programme. The report also explores some avenues for continuing the programme.

Skills4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

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DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
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DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Authors
v.0.1	03/06/2024	Document created with section outlines	Curtis Sharma
v.0.2	23/06/2025	Draft for task-internal review	Curtis Sharma, Jitka Stilund Hansen, Valentina Pasquale, Evgenios Vlachos, Thea Marie Drachen
v0.3	02/07/2025	Draft for project-internal review	Curtis Sharma, Jitka Stilund Hansen, Valentina Pasquale, Evgenios Vlachos, Thea Marie Drachen
v0.4	11/07/1015	Penultimate draft – incorporation of task-external reviewer comments	Curtis Sharma, Jitka Stilund Hansen, Valentina Pasquale, Evgenios Vlachos, Thea Marie Drachen
v1.0	04/08/2025	Final version	Claudio Prandoni, Sara Di Giorgio

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
Competence Centre	Competence Centre represents a point of reference in a specific Country/Region/Domain to find key competences to enable the practice of Open Science with adequate knowledge of standards, applications and tools and best practices for delivering, managing, re-using, sharing and analysing FAIR data, as well as other digital research objects.
Data Steward	Data stewards put Open Science and Research Data Management principles into practice: they work with stakeholders to establish, govern, and maintain processes to collect research data, make it usable for research objectives, facilitate its transformation into research output, assist in quality assurance, and support informed-decision making on its openness for reuse according to ethical, legal, and social expectations.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
Network	Expansive open chains of connections, without having a concept of membership, and little expectation of mutually supportive interaction
OS	Open Science
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management

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1 Executive summary

Skills4EOSC's core objective is to advance Open Science skills by unifying the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, closing the three gaps identified with respect to Open Science(OS) competences namely, (1) lack of OS and data expertise, (2) lack of a clear definition of data professional profiles and corresponding career paths and (3) fragmentation in training resources. One way to address these deficits is to facilitate the exchange of knowledge and expertise between research-performing institutions.

The Fellowship Programme was an integral part of the Skills4EOSC project, situated within work package 6 *Professional Networks for Lifelong Learning*. The programme was allotted dedicated funding and resources to support strengthening of competences of individual data professionals working with OS, FAIR and research data management (RDM). Its rollout was a flagship achievement for Skills4EOSC.

Given that these are constantly evolving domains, data professionals need to frequently refresh and update their competences. It was the aim of the Programme to support this upskilling process and also facilitate knowledge-exchange between research-performing institutions.

We invited partner institutions in the Skills4EOSC consortium to participate in the programme as host institutions. Through a light-weight application procedure, we provided two calls for fellowships of 1-3 months duration. Nine fellowships were awarded. At the end of each placement, both fellow and host completed a survey to evaluate their experience. Professional competences gained or used were compared to the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) Profile for data stewards (R7), developed in work package 2 of the Skills4EOSC project.

It was concluded that the Fellowship Programme offered a unique and valuable opportunity to use and develop competences of relevance for a career as data professional or data steward. At the same time, the fellows' evaluation of the MVS profile for data steward supported its relevance.

The report also highlights a gap in awareness of dedicated professional development opportunities. The ERASMUS+ and certain university network staff mobility programmes can support among other things, continued competence development in the RDM and OS area. Avenues for sustainability of the fellowship programme through the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network and other EOSC projects are also discussed.

The appendices contain materials for reuse, including the call text, templates and survey questions.

2 Background of the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

The main goal of the Skills4EOSC project has been to harmonise the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, and to sustain this ecosystem. The project aimed to accelerate the upskilling of European researchers and data professionals in the field of FAIR and Open Data, intensive-data science and Scientific Data Management. The creation of a number of national Competence Centres (CCs) coordinated in a pan-European CC Network is seen as the main instrument to offer or coordinate training, support, empowerment, lifelong learning, professionalisation, and resources to benefit a variety of stakeholders, including data stewards and data professionals in general.

The Fellowship Programme was a flagship achievement of the Skills4EOSC project and a main deliverable of WP6. The Programme sponsored short training periods (i.e., secondments) in Open Science for data professionals across Europe. This initiative was tailored for (aspiring) data stewards, and other individuals engaged in data support related to Open Science, collectively referred to hereafter as "Fellows". The Programme played a fundamental role in fostering professional recognition of Open Science support and in fostering connections and knowledge exchange between professionals, institutions and peer networks, either already existing or created through task 3.1. The Programme's primary objectives were to:

- **Support Life-Long Learning:** Encourage data professionals in Open Science to acquire skills relevant to Open and FAIR data practices and research data management, fostering continuous professional growth.
- **Build Institutional Capacity:** Empower Fellows to build or consolidate Open and FAIR data practices within their home institutions, driving positive organisational change.
- **Enable Knowledge Exchange:** Enable Fellows to explore, establish, and share services, tools, and infrastructures related to Open and FAIR data.
- **Strengthen Collaboration:** Facilitate collaboration among institutions by encouraging participation in relevant professional networks, creating a vibrant community of data professionals.

Given that Open Science and RDM according to the FAIR principles are quickly evolving domains reflecting the innovative nature of research, professionals need to constantly refresh and update their competences to work effectively. It was the aim of the Programme to support this upskilling process.

3 Development and Rollout

3.1 Design and Initiation

The Fellowship Programme was proposed to run over two calls. The first call was launched in August 2023 at the end of the first year of the Skills4EOSC project. The call text is found in Appendix A1. To prepare for this milestone, task members needed to define the target professionals as well as the application and evaluation processes within the scope and financial scope of the Skills4EOSC project. The total budget was set at 40,000 euro intended to support eight placements (four in each call)

3.1.1 Defining the target professionals

The Fellowship Programme targeted data professionals in research-performing organisations working or aspiring to work in Open Science, RDM and FAIR data. Researchers were welcome to apply, but the targeted roles were data stewards, data librarians, RDM specialists, etc., as defined in Wildgaard et al., 2020 (R1) which focus on data support. There was no limit with regard to the professional seniority of the applicants; individuals aspiring to be data stewards, early-career and advanced-career candidates were welcome to apply.

The Fellowship Programme welcomed applications from candidates at Skills4EOSC partners, as well as from outside the consortium. Applicants were limited to those affiliated with a publicly funded research-performing organisation in an EU or EU-widening country (R2). The applicant would need to comply with the adopted Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions mobility rule (described in Appendix A1).

3.1.2 Recruiting host institutions

Host institutions were limited to those within the consortium due to the funding structure in the Skills4EOSC project, which prohibited transfer of grant funds to non-partner institutions. Emails were sent to all consortium partners informing them about the Fellowship Programme and inviting them to sign up as a potential host institution (appendix 1). This invitation was also extended during Skills4EOSC plenaries and Technical Board meetings. We did not perform an assessment of eligibility of the host institution or require a formal training or data steward programme being offered to the applicant. However, it was required that all potential host institutions must have a research data management and support service in place. This can be through library services, scholarly communications

offices, local DCCs, a Data Steward programme, etc. They should also be able to support competence development in Open Science and/or RDM (see FAQs appendix 2 for more detail).

Participating institutions were listed on the [Fellowship Programme web page](#) as part of the call text. Institutions had the option to include details about their RDM and OS programmes and initiatives and the placement options they offered (section 3.1.3). nine out of 12 institutions did this (see appendix 3). Interested candidates were required to contact the institutions and together with them create and agree on the content and structure of a placement to be presented in their application. The quality of the proposal depended in part on the ability and suitability of the host’s RDM and OS offices to support the placement and to benefit the exchange of knowledge and expertise. The For the first call, 12 institutions offered to be hosts with 10 of these also offering placements during the second call (Table 1).

Table 1 – Participant institutions in the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

<i>Host institution</i>	<i>Projects applied or reapplied for/projects obtained</i>
<i>Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), IT</i>	1/1
<i>Polytechnic University of Turin, IT</i>	1/0
<i>University of Trento, IT</i>	2/0
<i>Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change, IT</i>	0
<i>4TU.ResearchData, NL</i>	3/2
<i>TU Delft, NL</i>	1/0
<i>Technical University of Denmark (DTU), DK</i>	1/1
<i>Aarhus University, DK</i>	0
<i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), DE</i>	4/2
<i>KU Leuven, BE</i>	1/1
<i>University of Edinburgh (UoE), UK</i>	1/1
<i>Chalmers University of Technology (CUT), SE</i>	2/1

Skills4EOSC gratefully acknowledges these institutions for offering to host a fellow during the Programme. The table indicates how many applications were made involving each host institution and how many were successful.

3.1.3 Structure of the Fellowship

After presenting the fellowship opportunity to the [Danish National RDM Network](#), we obtained valuable feedback on content and duration. Concern was raised that the initial goal of a 3-month fellowship could hamper many from applying, as without interim cover, human resources could be insufficient at the home institution.

Therefore, it was agreed that a placement should last minimum one month and maximum three months. If split across multiple stays, placements must still be completed within three months. The fellowship could take three forms:

- A project proposed by the fellow, aligned with and supported by an office or faculty of the host institution;
- An already existing project running at the host institution, which the fellow could join and contribute to;
- An internship where the fellow observes and participates in day-to-day activities in research data support at the host institution; this could be within one office/department or across several.

In this way, fellows would have the opportunity to build on existing skills and/or obtain new ones by having an immersive experience. Overall, the goal was to be of benefit to the fellow's career. Refer to Appendix A1 for the call text.

An non-negotiable condition was that the salary of the fellow should continue to be covered by the home institution for the entire duration of the fellowship. Travel, accommodation, participation in any relevant training would be covered, however daily allowances or equipment costs were not eligible (see call text in Appendix A1).

3.1.4 Application process

For ease of application and evaluation, a short application and CV form was designed, through which basic information about applicant, the home and host institutions were supplied. There was also a basic budget template to provide information about expected/allowed costs (Appendix A2). The application was managed through EUSurvey (R3). Task 6.4 members constituted the Fellowship Secretariat to which any questions could be addressed via dedicated email: fellowship@lists.skills4eosc.eu.

Fellowship calls were announced at least 2 months before the application deadline (Table 2). Reviewers then had 2 weeks to evaluate applications; see section 3.3 below further details on the evaluation process. The call stipulated that a granted fellowship must be started within one year after notification of

acceptance, thereby leaving time to complete the reimbursement and reporting before the end of the Skills4EOSC project on 31 August 2025. The second call was therefore announced shortly after the application deadline of the first.

Table 2 - Timeline for the Fellowship calls

Call	Announcement date	Application deadline	Response date	Latest start date of fellowship
<i>Call 1</i>	31 August 2023	31 October 2023	12 December 2023	12 December 2024
<i>Call 2</i>	21 December 2023	29 February 2024 (extended to 17 March 2024)	29 April 2024	29 April 2025

Calls were released and promoted via the Skills4EOSC webpage (R4), through emails to all consortium partners, social media platforms and EOSC-related channels.

Table 3 – How applicants learned about the call (n=16). Answers collected from the application template

Communication channel	Number of applicants
<i>Word of mouth/colleague</i>	6
<i>Organisation email/news</i>	3
<i>EOSC-related channel</i>	4
<i>Social Media</i>	3

Experience with the application process was evaluated by successful candidates in their Fellowship reports and was evaluated as easy (mean score 4.1: 1 = very difficult; 2 = difficult; 3 = neutral; 4 = easy; 5 = very easy).

3.2 Evaluation process

The evaluation form was inspired by the “Guide for Applicants” from the AIAS-COFUND II Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellowship programme (R5), and adapted to the Skills4EOSC requirements (Appendix A3). All applications were screened

for completeness and eligibility (see section 3.1.1) before being passed on to assigned evaluators.

Evaluators were recruited from across the Skills4EOSC consortium. They were complemented by international colleagues familiar with data stewardship. A pool of 13. Five of these were working in Skills4EOSC*, three were at Skills4EOSC partner institutions but not involved in the project** and three were at non-partner institutions***) reviewers were recruited for the first call and they remained available for the second call. For each call, the Fellowship Secretariat assessed conflicts of interest with applicants, home or host institutions. Eventually nine of the potential evaluators reviewed applications (Table 4).

Table 4 – List of Evaluators

Evaluator	ORCID	Organisation
<i>Katrine Weisteen Bjerde*</i>	0000-0003-3413-4464	Directorate for higher education and skills, Norway
<i>Fotis Mystakopoulos*</i>	0000-0002-9354-3754	OPERAS Research Infrastructure, Greece
<i>Thea Marie Drachen*</i>	0000-0003-4760-5536	University of Southern Denmark, Denmark
<i>Ugo Moschini*</i>	0000-0002-8006-6039	Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Italy
<i>Aoife Coffey***</i>	0000-0001-5008-3711	University College Cork, Ireland
<i>Antti Rousi**</i>	0000-0002-4184-7035	Aalto University, Finland
<i>Federica Cappelluti*</i>	0000-0003-4485-9055	Politecnico di Torino, Italy
<i>Richard Dennis**</i>	0000-0002-4472-7194	University of Copenhagen, Denmark
<i>Reinder Radersma***</i>	0000-0001-8186-6348	NWO-I Digital Competence Center, Netherlands

Skills4EOSC gratefully acknowledge the above persons for their contribution to the Fellowship Programme

Evaluators would be limited to reviewing only two applications each with a turnaround period given a review deadline of 14 days.

Each application was assessed by two evaluators according to the evaluation form (Appendix A3). The application was given a score (between 1 (poor) - 5 (excellent)) based on the profile of the applicant (50%). Criteria here focused on professional experience in relation to the proposed project, motivation and suitability of applicant and skills to be gained and/or potential benefits for the home institution. Quality of the proposal counted for the remaining 50% and the

quality of the proposal (50%). Criteria here focused on merits and thoroughness of the proposed project, feasibility (considering time, resources and available support from host institution), the potential for transferring of skills, suitability of selected host institute for the proposed placement and justification of requested resources. The mean score was used to rank the applications. The four highest ranking applicants were awarded a fellowship in each call. In the second call, five fellowships were awarded as the budget allowed for this

Table 5 – Number of applicants and awarded fellowships as well as evaluation scores for each call.

<i>Call</i>	<i>No. of applicants</i>	<i>No. of fellowships awarded</i>	<i>Range of evaluation scores</i>	<i>Female among applicants/ females awarded</i>
<i>Call 1</i>	9	4	2.25 - 5	4/3
<i>Call 2</i>	8 (3 applicants from Call 1)	5	3 - 4.75	4/2

The total budget for the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme was 40,000 Euro, with a maximum budget of 5.000 Euro per applicant. Four fellowships were granted in the first call (Table 5). For the second call, we were able to award five fellowships, as the total budget of the five top-ranking applicants could be accommodated within the total budget. There was virtually even distribution of gender among applicants (8 females, 9 males, Table 5) and awardees (5 females and 4 males). The selection of host institutions was well distributed geographically, with only KIT and 4TU.ResearchData hosting two fellows, one in each call; at KIT each fellow was affiliated with distinct departments.

All successful and unsuccessful applicants and host institutions were notified at the same time, six weeks after the application deadline.

Table 6 – Duration of the awarded fellowships

<i>Duration of fellowship</i>	<i>1 month</i>	<i>2 months</i>	<i>3 months</i>
<i>No. of fellows</i>	2	4	3

Applications were received from 8 EU countries and one EU Widening country, Albania. Table 7 shows the geographical spread of applicants and successful fellows. Figure 1 shows the breadth of the fellowship programme mapping the host institution countries (Table 1) with the successful fellows countries (Table 7).

Table 7 – Geographical spread of applicants (n=17) and successful fellows (n=9).

<i>Country of fellow</i>	<i>No. of applications for a fellowship</i>	<i>No. of successful applications</i>
<i>Germany</i>	3*	2
<i>Belgium</i>	2*	1
<i>Hungary</i>	3*	
<i>Czech Republic</i>	2	2
<i>Poland</i>	1	1
<i>Portugal</i>	1	1
<i>Spain</i>	3	2
<i>Italy</i>	1	
<i>Albania</i>	1	

**includes applications to both calls by the same applicant.*

Figure 1 – Map of Europe showing the host institutions and their countries (orange) as well as the successful fellows countries (blue). Countries both hosting and providing fellows appear in green.

3.3 Reports from fellows and host institutions

To enable comparison of their experience and to evaluate the success off the programme, fellows were required to complete a report about their placements. Two surveys were created in EUSurvey to facilitate reporting. After each placement was completed, the relevant fellow and host institution contact were invited to access the survey and provide their feedback. These reports are analysed in Section 4. After all placements were completed, the Secretariat issued a certificate to all fellows.

4 Outcomes and value of the Fellowship Programme

4.1 Survey results – Fellows

All fellows expressed that the targets in their applications were met, largely due to well-prepared and realistic projects, but also through being embedded in a well-organised team. For example, one fellow was supporting a department at their host organisation. Although content was frequently changed, the support they received from the RDM team allowed the project to be adapted to meet those new demands.

In evaluating the overall satisfaction with regard to fulfilling the learning and knowledge exchange targets set out in their proposal, most fellows found it highly satisfactory (Fig. 2). This was supported by the high satisfaction with the experience at their host institution (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – After finalising their fellowship, fellows were asked about their satisfaction with different aspects of the Programme and overall

Some placements were via internship where fellows learned about the daily operations of the host organisation; meeting with different research services and obtaining knowledge about diverse services in library and data support. Fellows

encountered activities in affiliated teams such as scholarly communication, bibliometric analysis, legal advice, IT, infrastructure, tools and training services.

This provided good understanding *“about the different services that research data management intersects with. The number of procedures and interactions needed to provide an effective service is large and complex, and depends on the size of the institution, the amount of financial and human resources available, the policies and infrastructure in place, and the quality and health of the collaborations and interactions.”* (quote from survey).

Fellows were exposed to a wide range of tasks related to data stewardship and research data management (RDM) services, which inspired them to consider new career directions.

“It was essential to see and experience data stewardship practices on site at a large university abroad which will make a huge difference in decisions/paths taken in the future, I believe.” (quote from survey).

The experiences also highlighted the value of good interpersonal skills, when providing RDM services.

“Success comes from the healthy and effective relationships with different stakeholders.” (quote from survey).

“It became clear that a project like this is not just about expertise, but also about interpersonal skills: it is all about communication.” (quote from survey).

One fellow was deeply inspired how the host, who was also a group leader, and who *“supports and motivates creativity and critical thinking, as well as ... welcomes opinions and is open to new ideas. This training inspired me to look for work in a team like this and be a leader like that.”* (quote from survey).

Overall, this highlights that the fellowship programme went beyond working on a specific project—it broadened the fellows’ perspectives on the many possibilities within RDM services and emphasized the value of developing soft skills for professional growth.

4.1.1 Tangible outcomes

The fellows were asked to list any tangible outcomes from their work in the host institutions and below are the provided outputs.

Infrastructures and tools:

- Technical updates and prototype of a system that will help researchers manage their research data
- A DMP template, currently under construction and not publicly available
- A webpage profile for 4TUResearchData community members. Here is an [example](#)
- An RDM system based on an electronic lab notebook, where versioning of data includes the data and any previous notes and practices related to the data
- In progress: [Mantra RDM Training](#)

Outputs related to training or implementation of RDM practices:

- [Skills4EOSC Data Steward Curriculum Pilot Training Ontologies](#)
- An internal report about implementation of the institutional RDM policy at a scientific department
- A template for workshops at departments/ with researchers to create awareness about RDM needs
- Design templates for planning metadata courses
- Started co-authoring a paper with one of the 4TU.ResearchData team members about secondary uses of research data. To be published in 2025

Two posts about the experiences were also written. Both in English and openly available:

- [Edinburgh Research Data Blog Skills4EOSC fellowship](#)
- [Get inspiration from a visiting fellow - European collaboration strengthens our competences](#)

4.1.2 Networking and funding opportunities

The fellows were asked if they are members of an RDM/Open Science/FAIR/data steward network or community and all were members of or engaged with work in such communities (Table 8).

Table 8 – Fellows’ memberships in International or national RDM/Open Science/FAIR/data steward network or communities

International networks

National networks

EOSC task forces	Network of Open Science Competences, a Polish data steward network
Research Data Alliance, WGs and IGs	Participant of the Data Stewardship goes Germany Workshops
Member of editorial board of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace	Open Science Community Lisboa
FAIRsharing Community Champions Programme	Collective Open Access Perú
ELIXIR RDM Community	Portuguese Data Stewards Network
European Association of Research Managers and Administrators	Dutch Data Steward interest group
	Flemish Research Data Network

Although the fellows were all engaged in Open Science, FAIR, RDM or data steward communities, none of them were aware of any funding opportunities comparable to the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme.

4.1.3 Conclusion: Fellowship Programme and funding opportunities

The above expressions and listed outcomes, together with the highly satisfactory rating of the fellowship (Fig. 1), showed that the possibility to have a focused, well-organised stay in another environment was a highly valuable professional development opportunity. The lack of knowledge of comparable funding opportunities indicates a gap in professional development opportunities for data professionals working with RDM and Open Science.

4.2 Survey results – host institutions

All institutions mentioned a positive experience with knowledge exchange and some with continued cooperation between the host institution and the fellow home institution. When evaluating the overall satisfaction regarding the fellowship, the placement benefit and the benefit to the host institution, all were satisfied and most host institutions found them very satisfactory (Fig. 2).

Descriptive answers to questions on different aspects of the programme (anonymized and simplified) are presented below.

Figure 3 – After finalising the fellowship, host institution representatives (n=8) were asked about their satisfaction with different aspects of the programme

4.2.1 Open-ended Questions

To present the results of the following open-ended questions of the survey in a meaningful manner we decided to read through the provided answers and summarize them into a paragraph:

- How well do you feel your institution/office/project benefited from hosting your fellow?
- In your opinion, how well did the placement benefit the fellow?
- Were the resources you put into the fellowship worth the outcome?
- Do you have any comments or suggestions for improvement for future fellowship programmes?

Across the various host institutions, a number of recurring themes emerged that highlight the overall success and added value of the fellowship exchanges. Most notably, hosts consistently emphasized the mutual benefit derived from the experience—fellows brought fresh perspectives and out-of-the-box thinking that enriched local practices (Host 1, Host 2, Host 8), while also gaining valuable insights into institutional workflows and approaches (Host 3, Host 4). Fellows were often able to make meaningful contributions to ongoing projects, particularly in areas such as research data management planning, tool development, and training materials (Host 5, Host 6, Host 1). Their enthusiasm, professionalism, and ease of integration into existing teams were frequently commended (Host 3, Host 6, Host 4). Many hosts appreciated the flexible structure of the fellowship, which allowed activities to be tailored to the specific context and needs of both parties (Host 6, Host 2, Host 8). Some challenges were also reported, including administrative complexities related to non-EU fellows (Host 3). Further, engaging research groups with little RDM experience was a challenge (Host 4). However, such experience also reflects what can be expected when doing consultations for research groups that have no or few RDM practices in place. Nonetheless, these situations were also seen as learning opportunities, highlighting the importance of interpersonal and translational skills for successful RDM engagement (Host 4). Several institutions noted that a longer fellowship duration—three months or more—would have been beneficial to deepen collaboration and maximize impact (Host 1, Host 4). Representative quotes from the host institutions are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 – Quotes from Hosts

“...overall we were very satisfied with the application process and outcome.” (Host 1)

“Everybody was happy :)!” (Host 2)

“...improvements that we had not previously anticipated.” (Host 3)

“It is quite amazing how a relatively small grant can benefit the competences of a data professional.” (Host 4)

“... was worth doing.” (Host 5)

“It is good that there were not too many prescriptions and that the experience could be shaped by the fellow and the host.” (Host 6)

“Large added value and competence building.” (Host 7)

4.2.2 Funding opportunities

Host institutions were asked if they were aware of comparable funding opportunities for non-researcher data professionals. Most institutions answered no, one answered yes mentioning:

- ERASMUS workplace visits
- Una Europa Live My Life

4.2.3 Summary: host institutions' feedback

The above sentiments, ratings and descriptions of lessons learned points to successful exchanges of knowledge which do require organisation and preparation, but consistently has shown valuable output for both sides of the participation.

4.3 Skillset Comparison: Self-Evaluation vs. Minimum Viable Skillset Profile for Data Stewards

The [Catalogue of Minimum Viable Skillset \(MVS\) Profiles](#) is a resource that describes essential skills and concepts required to deliver Open Science (OS) outcomes for communities and organisations. It was developed by the Skills4EOSC project to help with skills development and curriculum design by connecting key competences to specific Open Science practices (explanation copied from R6 and R7). The MVS for data stewards comprises the skillset to implement Open Science (OS) practices, activities, etc., that may typically be expected of a data steward. The skillsets are described in R7; the skillsets outlined in the fellowship survey show minor deviations mainly due to wording (Table 9). Fellows were asked to scrutinise the MVS for data stewards and then think about which of these skills they either acquired or improved upon during the fellowship. Further, they were asked to indicate how important these skills are for good data stewardship. The skills are categorised as HARD and SOFT/TRANSVERSAL (see Table 9). For the survey, we used the terms HARD and SOFT.

Box 1 Questions responded to in Table 9

Question 1: Which of the HARD and SOFT skills did you acquire or improve during your fellowship?

Question 2: In your opinion, how essential are these skills for Data Stewards? Please consider either your own role or other people you worked with in the Data steward role, and rate each skills from 1 (not essential) to 5 (essential).

Table 9 – The fellows were asked to evaluate the *Minimum Viable Skillset for Data Stewards* developed by the Skills4EOSC project (R7)

HARD skills (black) and SOFT skills (blue)	Question 1 No. of fellows selecting the skill (n=9)	Question 2 Mean rating (n=9)
<i>Knowledge of Open Science practices, policies and regulation and translation of these (when necessary) to local context.</i>	6	4.8
<i>Service provision to support specific Open Science practices including: applying FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data curation, preservation, archiving and responsible re-use.</i>	6	4.6
<i>Knowledge about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, intellectual property rights, information security and risk management.</i>	9	5.0
<i>Awareness raising among data creators, users, and research stakeholders of the value of good data management.</i>	6	4.4
<i>Provide advice and support on use of infrastructure and tools for data storage, versioning, publishing, and documentation.</i>	7	4.8
<i>Support Open Science practices, policies and practices through training design and delivery.</i>	6	4.6
<i>Monitor the research and funding ecosystem, identifying conflicting motivations, drivers and incentives among different stakeholders.</i>	5	4.0
<i>Knowledge/awareness of programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies.</i>	3	4.1
<i>Conflict management/mediation with a patient, empathic approach.</i>	2	4.0
<i>Critical and analytical thinking</i>	6	4.7
<i>Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge their needs.</i>	8	4.7
<i>Creativity, curiosity, and openness with willingness to learn.</i>	9	4.8
<i>Team management and project management with results-oriented planning and organising.</i>	6	4.2

Perhaps not surprisingly, the top HARD skill improved or acquired was “*knowledge about RDM, (personal) data governance and ethics, intellectual property rights, information security and risk management*” reflecting that most fellowships were related to an RDM internship or project. The *knowledge of Open Science and translating for example policy into practice* was also a skill acquired or improved by most fellows, as was *providing advice on infrastructures and tools*. In line with the personal experience, these HARD skills received the highest ratings by the fellows, when asked about how essential the skill is for a data steward (Question 2, mean score = 4.8).

A top SOFT skill acquired or improved for most fellows was “*Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge their needs*”. “*Critical and analytical thinking*” as well as “*team and project management with result-oriented planning and organising*” were skills used by a majority of the fellows.

Two fellows had experience with “*conflict management*”, which they both rated as an essential skill (rating = 5). However, it was the skill regarded as the least essential by the fellows (mean score = 4.0). Since RDM services embrace a large stakeholder involvement, such a SOFT skill cannot be disregarded and its use may be highly depending on context and experience. This line of thought is supported by the high rating (mean score = 4.7) of ability to “*engage and network with stakeholders to bridge their needs*”.

Only three of the fellows had used “*Knowledge/awareness of programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies*”, which may reflect that such skills require a certain focus that is still not mainstream among RDM professionals. However, the skill is regarded as rather important for a data steward (= 4.1).

It is expected that a short secondment will demand much of a person, therefore all fellows had used their “*creativity, curiosity, and willingness to learn*”. Interestingly, this is also a SOFT skill rated as a highly essential skill by the fellows, perhaps reflecting the complexity of RDM services and the need to adapt and accommodate different (research) environments and stakeholders.

Based on the mean score of > 4 for all skillsets, it is clear that the fellows found the skills meaningful in relation to their personal knowledge and experience as data professionals. The results obtained here, although based on a few and specialised professionals, do support that persons aiming for a career as data professional within research data management and Open Science will benefit from competence development related to the developed MVS profile for data stewards.

4.4 Conclusion: value of the Fellowship Programme

The skills and profile of data stewards have been analysed in a few reports only (R1, R7). Therefore, training opportunities and curricula have been scarce (with a few exceptions, e.g., R8) until the Skills4EOSC project embarked on analysing needs and developing resources for this. The Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme offered a unique and valuable opportunity to use and develop competences of relevance for a career as data professional or data steward. At the same time, the fellows' evaluation of the MVS profile for data steward highlighted its relevance.

5 Recommendations and future

5.1 Possible areas for improvement

In the end, the Secretariat felt there should have been more strict rules about multiple stays. We offered applicants the possibility to have a placement lasting between 1-3 months. Perhaps, we should have stipulated as part of the conditions, that no visit should be less than one month at a time. If one month is too long, for instance in the case of parents, then a stipulation could be no more than one week between visits. While it is acknowledged (as in section 3.1.3) that for example, long periods of absence from a home institution could adversely affect a department or the individual's work, this would contribute to a more focused and immersive experience, perhaps richer for both host and fellow, and would have saved on travel, as well as been more climate-minded. A further improvement could be to create a "Data Stewardship Ambassador" programme through which awardees could be asked to share their experiences and any new skills or knowledge gained through the Fellowship Programme. This could be done through stipulating a number of talks to give or a period of time, say one year, during which this type of activity should take place.

5.2 Sustainability

The Fellowship Programme has shown that (human) barriers appear to be low for individuals who wish to organise secondments abroad. All fellows could go through the secondments with full salary from their home institution, and the host institutions were happy to engage in projects and internships with the visiting fellows. Most institutions are familiar with this type of exchange from their research environments. However, the main obstacle is still to obtain funding for travel and accommodation abroad or identifying and participating in dedicated training opportunities. Many traditional university funders are focused on research projects and less on data management or Open Science competences.

This is reflected in the fact that none of the fellows were aware of funding opportunities comparable to the Fellowship Programme. However, one host institution mentioned the Una Europa programme that offers the "Live My Life job-shadowing initiative" for non-academic staff at the European partner universities (R9). Further, the North2North staff mobility programme (R10) is a student, researcher and staff mobility programme offered by a collaboration of a range of Arctic universities. These and comparable programmes could offer an opportunity for professional development of employees wishing to upskill

research data management or other competences. However, identification of such programmes requires affiliation with a partner institution.

The ERASMUS+ programme offers training and teaching possibilities for staff (R11). A non-academic staff at one of the host institutions was inspired by the Fellowship Programme and searched for own training opportunities. The ERASMUS+ mobility programme provided funding for RDM training at another European university. Thus, opportunities already exist in the European funding schemes. However, many professionals are not aware of such mobility programmes.

5.2.1 Sustainability efforts arising from within Skills4EOSC

The main entity responsible for the sustainability and development of Skills4EOSC outcomes, outputs and achievements is the “National Competence Centre” (CC). Each national CC is part of the wider CC Network. Several working groups will be created within the CC Network aimed at sustaining and further developing specific Skills4EOSC outcomes. One such working group is expected, among other things, to focus on efforts to sustain the Fellowship programme either in the same or a similar fashion. Institutions and initiatives are being invited to join a group of Supporting Organisations, who will work collaboratively with CCs and the CC Network. Host and home institutions who participated in the fellowship programme during Skills4EOSC are being invited to join this group. These institutions, as well as others, will be invited to form a network of institutions who are interested in exchanges of data professionals based on the format of the Skills4EOSC programme or some refinement of it. Institutions could also be encouraged to make bespoke arrangements with others according to their focus and capacity.

5.2.2 Sustainability through other EOSC projects

The EU has an awareness of the need for training of infrastructure staff and data stewards. This is reflected in the HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-04 call *Data stewards, Skills and Training for Open Science and FAIR Practices*, which specifically mentions enhancing of data stewardship skills and mainstreaming and promoting of best practices in support of FAIR data and Open Science. As can be seen from responses to the host evaluation survey, meaningful value realised for both fellow and host that outweighed the investment of resources, with citations of new approaches, new and unanticipated competencies and improvements to RDM. The presence of fellows also seemed to highlight gaps in RDM capacity and awareness among researchers in some cases, which opens discussion on where and how RDM could be improved. Continuation of the

Skills4EOOSC fellowship programme, therefore, in some form, would serve the objectives of this new call, through experience with real-world problem solving and transfer of skills and knowledge that may not be possible otherwise. It is recommended by the Fellowship secretariat that the winning consortium consider this option. It will also benefit the efforts of the CC network working group mentioned above towards a more sustainable programme.

6 References

No	Description/Link
R1	Wildgaard, L., Vlachos, E., Nondal, L., Larsen, A. V., & Svendsen, M. (2020). National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum) (Version 1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3609516
R2	European Commission. Horizon Europe Widening - Who should apply https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-widening-who-should-apply_en Last accessed 20 Dec. 2023
R3	EUSurvey. https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/ Last accessed 5 Feb. 2025
R4	Skills4EOSC. Fellowship Programme. https://www.skills4eosoc.eu/participate/fellowship-programme . The webpage no longer contains the call information, but is updated with outcome of the Fellowship Programme on 11 Feb. 2025.
R5	Aarhus University Institute of Advanced Studies. AIAS-COFUND II Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellowship programme Guide for Applicants. https://aias.au.dk/fileadmin/www.aias.au.dk/Calls_for_Fellowships/Guide_applicants_AIAS_COFUNDII_2021.pdf Last accessed 24 Oct. 2024
R6	EOSC. Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles – Minimum Viable Skillsets. https://eosoc.eu/roadmap/catalogue-of-open-science-career-profiles-minimum-viable-skillsets/ Last accessed 5 Feb. 2025
R7	Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101902
R8	Master in Data Stewardship, University of Southern Denmark. https://www.sdu.dk/da/uddannelse/efter_videreuddannelse/master/data-stewardship Last accessed 17 June 2025.
R9	Una Europa. Get involved as a member of professional services staff. https://www.una-europa.eu/get-involved/as-a-member-of-university-staff Last accessed 28 May 2025.
R10	UArctic. Participate in north2north. https://www.uarctic.org/activities/north2north/north2north-for-staff-and-faculty/ Last accessed 11 Feb. 2025.
R11	ERASMUS+. Opportunities for individuals. https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/opportunities/opportunities-for-individuals Last accessed 28 May 2025.

7 Appendices

No	Description/Link
A1	Invitation letter to institutions to be a potential host
A2	FAQs for potential host institutions
A3	Published host information
A4	Application form
A5	Call information The text was published partly on https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/fellowship-programme and in full text as an application guide in EUSurvey
A6	Evaluation template
A7	Host institution feedback survey (published in EUSurvey)
A8	Fellow feedback survey (published in EUSurvey)
A9	Grant Certificate

Subject: Invitation to Participate in the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

Dear ["Right Person"],

We are delighted to invite [name of institution] to participate as a potential host in the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme. This programme aims to foster knowledge exchange and collaboration in the field of Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science (OS). As an institution dedicated to excellence in this domain, we believe your involvement would greatly contribute to the success of the programme.

The goal of the fellowship is to facilitate the exchange of expertise and skills between the fellow and the host institution. By hosting a fellow, you will have the opportunity to engage with current or aspiring Data Stewards/RDM Support Professionals from different countries and enhance the RDM services provided by your institution. This fellowship provides an excellent platform to build upon an established RDM service and explore new avenues in this rapidly evolving field.

The duration of the fellowship can be one, two or three months, and is intended as a focused and immersive experience. The fellow will be fully dedicated to their fellowship during this period, providing ample time for valuable knowledge transfer and project engagement. The call for candidates is set to go out during July 2023.

To support your institution's involvement, Skills4EOSC offers matched funding to cover the costs associated with hosting a fellow.

The fellowship can take one of three forms:

- **A project proposed by the fellow:** In this scenario, the fellow will conceive a project that aligns with the objectives and expertise of the host institution. This project could be undertaken within an office or faculty, allowing for a focused and impactful collaboration.
- **Joining a project proposed by the host institution:** Alternatively, the fellow can participate in an existing project proposed by your institution. This option provides an opportunity to leverage the fellow's skills and knowledge to advance ongoing initiatives.
- **An internship in research data support:** The fellow can also engage in an internship, where they will observe and actively participate in day-to-day activities related to research data support. This internship can span across one or multiple offices/departments, offering a comprehensive understanding of RDM practices within your institution.

As a host institution, we would kindly request you to provide an assigned mentor who will guide the fellow throughout their fellowship. The mentor will be responsible for regular contact hours to facilitate knowledge transfer, answer questions, and provide support as needed.

At the conclusion of the fellowship, the fellow will be expected to deliver a comprehensive report summarising their activities, achievements, and recommendations. We would also ask feedback from host institutions. These deliverables will serve as valuable outcomes, contributing to the overall knowledge exchange, furthering the advancement of RDM and OS practices, and contributing to the sustainability of the programme.

We believe that [institution]'s participation as a host will enrich the Fellowship programme and contribute to the development of a vibrant community of RDM and Open Science practitioners. We look forward to your positive response and the opportunity to collaborate on this exciting initiative.

Please let us know of your interest in participating as a host institution by **30 June 2023**. We would be happy to provide any additional information or answer any questions you may have.

Thank you for your consideration, and we look forward to the possibility of working together.

Sincerely,

Curtis Sharma

Skills4EOSC WP6 Lead

Additional information for potential host institutions in the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

What are the main objectives of the fellowship programme?

It supports the objective of Skills4EOSC in its goal of "unifying the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, in order to accelerate the upskilling of European researchers and data professionals in the field of FAIR and Open Data, intensive-data science and Scientific Data Management". RDM support (or "Data Stewardship" as it is being termed in Skills4EOSC) is still a nascent profession. There are not many formal/recognised training programmes for Data Stewardship. In addition, the knowledge and expertise required to be a Data Steward varies widely, depending on the research disciplines needing support. This means that training beyond a certain point cannot be generalised. It can therefore be very beneficial for those in such roles to work together to share their knowledge and experience and collaborate to find new, practical solutions. The ways in which Skills4EOSC envision this is through professional networks and through the Fellowship Programme. In WP6 we are supporting the creation of new Data Steward Networks (general and thematic) as well as piloting the Fellowship Programme, which we hope will continue and expand beyond Skills4EOSC.

Who can apply for the fellowship?

Strict rules on disbursement of funds only allow funds to be transferred to Skills4EOSC consortium partners. This restricts participation both as a potential host and as a fellow to only Skills4EOSC partners. Any research-performing partner can be a potential host and (aspiring) data professionals (data stewards and others working in RDM support relate to Open Science) from any partner can apply to be a fellow. This means that a partner institution could simultaneously host a fellow, while one of their employees is being hosted at another partner institution. We are however, working with the Skills4EOSC project officer to find some way to work around this so that we can facilitate applicants from non-consortium institutions. We will know of their decision by 15 July 2023.

How to apply?

The application form will be accessed through an EU Survey, where the applicant will fill in required information and submit supporting documents. These documents are: CV; fellowship proposal (including budget proposal); signed letter of support from their home institution; signed letter of acceptance from their chosen host institution. The signed letter of acceptance must indicate support for the candidate's proposal; information on how the proposal will be supported; specification of the length of the placement; and indication of commitment of a mentor for the duration of the placement. Crucially, this means that the applicant and the potential host institution must come to an agreement before the application is submitted.

How is the application evaluated?

The evaluation panel will be selected from across the Skills4EOSC consortium, after considering any conflicts of interest regarding both the applicant and the host institution. Applications will be assessed by at least two evaluators. Application will be assessed on the following criteria:

Applicant profile and motivation (50%)

- Motivation and suitability
- Professional qualifications
- Relevant experience and level of expertise
- Competences/skills to be gained and potential of the applicant to transfer the acquired skills to the home institution

Quality of the fellowship proposal (50%)

- Clear, convincing and compelling goals
- Feasibility: scientific, technological, access to infrastructure, project timeline, associated risks
- Appropriateness of requested resources
- Networking and dissemination
- An account of how both the host and the home institutions would receive added value for the fellowship undertaken

Are there any financial commitments for the host?

All costs relating to the fellowship will be met by the fellowship grant, providing they are directly related and are sufficiently justified, up to a maximum of 5K Euro (for a three-month long placement).

There are no per se financial commitments on the part of the host; we do not expect the host to anything outside of what they already do, or already have planned. Contribution is only expected to be in terms of time and support (a specified mentor is desired). If there are any costs directly related to the fellowship on the part of the host, such as course fees or facility access, and any necessary organizational costs, such as arranging an event to present the achieved results, or if there are additional costs associated with mentorship/supervision, then the fellowship grant will pay for these. They must all however, be justified in the candidate's budget proposal, which must be submitted along with the application. Part of the candidate's application is to include a letter of acceptance from the potential host institution and a budget proposal, where all expected direct expenses are to be included.

Travel, accommodation, meals, etc., will also be funded from the fellowship grant and must be justified in the budget proposal. We will ask home institutions to arrange travel/health insurance, as this would be most straightforward.

How are funds disbursed?

The rules for disbursement of funds in the project are quite strict, and the plan put forward by the Skills4EOSC coordinators is currently along the following lines. TU Delft, as the Skills4EOSC partner in charge of the fellowship programme will be responsible for disbursing funds. At the moment funds can only be transferred to institutions who are partners in the Skills4EOSC consortium. This limits participation, but together with the S4E Project Officer, we are trying to find ways around this. Only Skills4EOSC consortium partners can currently be host institutions. If the successful fellow comes from a Skills4EOSC partner, then we will send all funds to their home institution, who will be responsible for paying funds to the fellow and for transferring funds to the host institution if need be (and was part of the approved budget). This would be the simplest scenario. If we manage to accommodate applicants from institutions outside the Skills 4EOSC consortium, then TU Delft would have to pay funds directly to the fellow (and the host institution if need be).

Can the experience involve visiting our affiliated institutions?

It is possible to involve affiliated organisations to expanding the stay beyond the host institution; this will add value to the experience. All formal arrangements, however, will need to remain between Skills4EOSC, the fellow and the original host institution. We cannot, at least in the pilot stages of the fellowship, have multiple agreements. If you would like to include stays other institutions, then you are certainly welcome to coordinate this yourself. We are also not able at this time to disburse funds to institutions outside the Skills4EOSC consortium.

What is the proposed timeline?

- Secure potential host participation - 30 June 2023 (or thereabouts)
- Advertise call - by mid-August 2023
- Deadline for applications - 31 October 2023
- Selection of successful candidates - 31 December 2023
- Fellowship begins - no later than 12 months after being accepted
- Final report (fellow) on the experience to be delivered to host institution - one month after completion of the fellowship. A template will be provided
- Final report (institution) on the experience and fellow's report delivered to Skills4EOSC two months after end of fellowship. A template will be provided
- The second call will open in October 2023 with a deadline of 29 February 2024

Other important details

It will be up to the applicant to contact the potential host institution of their choice and determine whether it is possible for them to carry out the fellowship there. They will have to have a signed letter of acceptance from the potential host institution to this effect. The applicant will have to show that their presence at the host institution will benefit their career and present role, and they will have to evidence how their goals align with the align and support those of the host institution (whether centrally or in a particular faculty). The applicant will have to prove also that they have secured a dedicated mentor at the host institution (evidenced in the signed letter of acceptance). The applicant will also need a letter of support from their home institution. There is a mobility clause in the call which follows the MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions) mobility rule. The applicants must NOT have resided or carried out their main activities (work, studies etc.) for more than 12 months in the host organisation's country in the three years immediately prior to the application deadline. The placement is in person and must be continuous, that is, there can be no absences except in the cases of illness or emergency.

This document contains information that will be displayed on the Fellowship web page to be hosted on the Skills4EOSC website.

Blurb for call

Call document (download?)

Participating Institutions

- Name
- Links
- Placement options
- Contact person

Link to (EU Survey) Application

Title of Webpage: Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme for Data Professionals

Blurb for call – Intro from call document and a bit more

There is increasing need for research-performing organisations to develop and sustain professional profiles related to Open Science, FAIR data and research data management practices. For this reason, the Skills4EOSC Horizon Europe project will sponsor short secondments for (aspiring) data professionals in Open Science (i.e., data stewards and other individuals working in data support relating to Open Science) hereinafter “Fellowship Programme”. Therefore, the Fellowship Programme intends to stimulate life-long learning (knowledge and experience exchange) between data professionals at different institutions and participation to relevant professional networks.

The first call is now open and we invite applications from (aspiring) data professionals for placements at one of 11 participating institutions. The deadline for application is 31 October 2023. See here for details of the call and click here to apply. See below for a list of participating institutions. **Please contact individual institutions directly to find out more about their RDM support and Open Science services and to plan your fellowship proposal prior to submitting your application.**

Participating institutions

4TU.ResearchData

[4TU.ResearchData](#)

A fellowship at 4TU.ResearchData can take the form of joining an ongoing project, an internship working across different teams for example with the repository or community team, or a candidate can propose a project of their own, which aligns with the goals and activities of 4TU.ResearchData. The placement will last for three months. The fellow can expect to advance their knowledge on FAIR data and open science within science, engineering and design disciplines. They will understand how large research-intensive organisations operate within the Netherlands, become familiar with the national (Dutch) and international landscape on open science and FAIR Data and build personal and professional networks within their area of work/interest.

There are currently three projects which a fellow could join. These are from the community aspect. There will also be opportunities to work with the repository team:

Community platform development

The fellow will co-develop our community platform together with our technical team and guided by the community manager. [The 4TU.ResearchData community](#) hosts more than 200 researchers, staff and students from different fields and all working with research data and software. Our community is growing, and it needs a platform to combine with the newly developed repository system (open-source) to communicate, share information and tips, review each other work and collaborate on different projects. Research community-based platforms in the scientific field, prepare, share and collect information via survey getting in touch with our key community members, make recommendation and start setting up a platform.

Support the Data and Software Academy project

The fellow will support the development of the courses for the Data and Software Academy pilot in collaboration with a national team of Research data Management specialists, fellows and staff members of 4TU.ResearchData. According to the period the fellow will join us, they will be contribute to a phase: developing workshop for students (in the field of data and software interoperability), help with running the workshop and support the students with their projects, collect feedback and prepare a report about the course.

Data and Art exhibition collaborator

At 4TU.ResearchData we want to foster an exchange between art and data through data visualization. Our goal is to challenge artists to translate impactful data into artistic expression. The idea is for artists to give voice to data and make the process as reproducible as you would expect from a research process. Can we make data-inspired art reproducible? With existing publications from our researchers at the member institutions we will explore data visualization in collaboration with 4 art academies which will deliver an artist specialized in a specific disciplined art form. The end result will be presented at a grand exhibition at a museum in June 2024. The fellow will be involved in working with the art students to support them with data-related questions, and help them collecting and sharing information about their artistic process. The fellow/intern will also collaborate with the 4TU.ResearchData team in setting up the exhibition, collect feedback and prepare the information to be shared on the website and social media.

Please contact us to plan your proposal.

Contact: Madeleine de Smaele, M.M.E.deSmaele@tudelft.nl

Aarhus University (AU)

[Research Data Management at AU Library](#)

[Open Science at AU Library](#)

Please contact AU to find out more about their plans for the fellowship

Contact: Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard, bcd@au.dk

Chalmers University of Technology (Chalmers)

[Chalmers e-Commons](#)

Information for applicants: Chalmers suggests projects aligning with the following themes
These projects could also lead to a collaborative paper after the fellowship period if the fellow is interested:

1. Reviewing and summarising Swedish and European funding agencies' requirements for 'trusted' data repositories and the definitions of and requirements for trust in this context.

2. Developing, together with Chalmers e-Commons, a new Data Management Plan model for Data Stewardship Wizard which can be used to fulfil multiple funding requirements/recommendations for DMPs. This project would require a good amount of collaboration with the rest of the data management team at Chalmers.
3. Developing, together with Chalmers e-Commons, new training material to be used in research data management training. Knowledge of the Carpentries framework can be meritable.
4. Develop a method to identify and harvest information from data availability statements in academic publications
5. Identify barriers for research collaboration between private actors and Chalmers and/or organizations in multiple countries, with a focus on data sharing.

The host infrastructure will be Chalmers e-Commons , Chalmers' gateway to a collection of local, national, and international digital expert functions and resources. Researchers, research groups and research infrastructures at Chalmers can turn to e-Commons for support in making large-scale computing calculations/analyses, applying AI and Machine Learning in research and managing research data throughout its life cycle. Chalmers Data Office is a group within e-Commons specifically dealing with Research Data Management.

Contact: Jeremy Azzopardi, jeremyaz@chalmers.se

Delft University of Technology (TU-Delft)

[Research Data Management at TU Delft](#)

[TU Delft Research Data Management Policy](#)

[Data Stewardship at TU Delft](#)

[Open Science at TU Delft](#)

The fellow will work on a new or ongoing project proposed by the TU Delft Research Data and Software service. The project aims to improve services around research data and software management, and/or Data Stewardship. The placement at TU Delft will last for 3 months. During the project, the fellow will collaborate with various stakeholders including researchers, Data Stewards, Data Managers, RSEs, RDM trainers, and other research services.

Contact: Yan Wang, Y.Wang-16@tudelft.nl

Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC)

<https://www.cmcc.it/>

[CMCC Advanced Scientific Computing Division](#)

CMCC will offer the option to join an ongoing project, in which the fellow will be committed to supporting the ASC division project activities, ranging from the optimization of climate models to the design and implementation of Data Science solutions. In addition, the candidates might be involved in the design and development of ML/AI techniques applied to climate change. More relevant details will be worked out with the candidate according to their qualifications and interests. Projects at CMCC would suit candidates with some of the following qualifications and experience:

M.Sc. degree in Computer science or computer engineering

Expertise in programming (Python or FORTRAN)
Expertise in data base design
Expertise in sensors network
Preferred knowledge in parallel programming
Preferred knowledge in climate data analytics
Preferred knowledge in edge computing

Contact: Fabrizio Antonio, fabrizio.antonio@cmcc.it

Italian Institute of Technology (IIT)

<https://www.iit.it/open-science-and-research-data-management>

Following international guidelines and inspired by values of reproducibility and efficiency, IIT recognizes the importance to manage research data in a responsible way. Research Data Management (RDM) has been a priority for IIT since 2018, when dedicated resources were invested to create support services for scientists. In parallel, IIT has sustained Open Science practices, as means to promote dissemination of IIT results, to increase knowledge transfer, and to stimulate trust in Science and Technology, also with an educational and societal commitment. RDM support at IIT covers the following areas:

Planning research. IIT provides professional support to its scientists in creating data management plans (DMPs), including guidelines and tailored templates. A support working group for DMP writing has been created, involving IT, legal, technology transfer professionals, and data curators.

Working with data. IIT has adopted an Information Security policy that guides researchers in data protection depending on the risk classification. IIT provides IT and legal support to researchers for the correct management of personal and high-risk data, as well as tailored storage and backup solutions for different volumes and types of data.

Publishing and preserving. IIT has set up its own institutional research data repository, [IIT Dataverse](#), which allows data to be shared according to the FAIR principles, cited, and linked to scientific articles by assigning digital persistent identifiers. IIT Dataverse is one of the first Italian instances of Dataverse, is catalogued in re3data.org, and integrated with OpenAIRE Explore. RDM support has produced several guidelines and procedures to help researchers to use IIT Dataverse and other repositories.

Fellows at IIT could work on one of the following projects / activities, all aimed at improving the current RDM service:

- *Custom DMP templates for disciplines:* extend existing or create new templates for different disciplinary contexts, optionally using tools like Data Stewardship Wizard or DMPOnline.
- *Piloting data FAIRification:* collaborate with researchers in a selected domain of interest to develop workflows and procedures for the collection of metadata and documentation thus enabling FAIR data production.
- *Integrate Dataverse with external controlled vocabularies:* extend metadata schemas available in IIT Dataverse to support different disciplines and integrate it with external controlled vocabularies using available features.

Contact: Valentina Pasquale, Valentina.Pasquale@iit.it

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

[Research data management at KIT](#)

The [Karlsruhe Institute of Technology \(KIT\)](#) is “The Research University in the Helmholtz Association.” As the only German university of excellence with a national large-scale research sector, KIT offers students, researchers, and employees unique learning, teaching, and working conditions. Presently, more than 9000 people are working at KIT, of which more than half are conducting research in a broad range of disciplines from natural sciences to engineering, to economics, to the humanities and social sciences. This makes KIT one of the largest science institutions in Europe.

Good research today must not only be rigorous, innovative and insightful - it also relies on good research data management. Therefore, the [support team RDM@KIT](#) promotes the topic of research data management at KIT. In the support team RDM@KIT, different service units of KIT cooperate across institutes. The main responsibility of the support team lies at the KIT Library and the Steinbuch Centre for Computing. Within the research services department of the KIT Library, you will be part of a friendly team of 15 people with heterogeneous study backgrounds working on many third-party funded projects, in a collegial working atmosphere and an attractive working environment.

The Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme at KIT provides insights into the daily work of the support team. This includes, among others, the involvement in the international registry of research data repositories [re3data](#) working group, the involvement in the KIT-internal repository for research data [RADAR4KIT](#) and the participation in specific open science projects. The Fellowship Programme provides an outstanding opportunity to network and exchange experiences with local data professionals and scientists.

Skills4EOSC collaborates with the third-party funded project [bwFDM](#) in the development of a certificate course on RDM. The aim of this course is to facilitate the training of data professionals at KIT and beyond. The Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme at KIT includes the development of this course, which may involve, but is not limited to, contributing conceptual input for the preparation of a course module or assisting in the implementation of a Train-the-Trainer concept on RDM. Tasks are carried out in close collaboration with members of the project teams.

We are looking forward to your application for a two to three month stay with us. If you have questions or ideas regarding the Fellowship Programme, please do not hesitate to [contact us](#).

Contact: Claudia Kramer, Sekretariat@bibliothek.kit.edu

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KUL)

[KUL Research Data Management](#)

[KUL Open Science](#)

[Research Support at KUL Libraries](#)

The fellow will be in close contact with research support staff of KU Leuven Libraries who are located across KU Leuven campuses and specifically those who provide research data support. This support is coordinated through the RDM Competence Centre (RDM-CC), a virtual collaboration across the ICT department, research coordination office and KU Leuven Libraries. Depending on the project or internship, the fellow thus has the opportunity to focus on more operational research data support (e.g. 1st or 2nd level support, participate in the organisation of training sessions or giving advice to researchers) or participate in one of the RDM-CC actions or projects with a broader scope or target.

Contact: [Johan Philips](#), johan.philips@kuleuven.be

Polytechnic University of Turin (POLITO)

[POLITO Website](#)

Information for applicants: please contact POLITO to find out more about their plans for the fellowship

Contact: Mauro Paschetta, mauro.paschetta@polito.it

Technical University of Denmark (DTU)

[DTU Library](#)

Information for applicants: DTU Library would like to collaborate with a fellow and proposes the following options for the fellowship:

- 1) A dedicated project concerned with communication and/or development of teaching materials related to research data management.
- 2) During the coming years, departments at DTU will implement the revised DTU's Policy for research data management. Different implementation projects supported by DTU Library will evolve and the fellow will be able to work on such a dedicated project.
- 3) Internship. The fellow can participate in DTU Library's work with data publication in our institutional repository, DTU Data, as well as with teaching and data management planning activities. DTU Library is actively engaged in several national and international fora and the fellow can participate in these activities.

Option 3) should preferably be combined with a dedicated project as in 1) or 2) or as suggested by the fellow.

[Research Data Management at DTU](#)

[Open Science at DTU](#)

Information for applicants: please contact DTU to find out more about their plans for the fellowship

Contact: Katrine Flindt Holmstrand, kafh@dtu.dk

University of Edinburgh (UE)

[UE Research Data Service](#)

[Edinburgh Datashare Repository](#)

[UE Research Data Management Policy](#)

[Open Research Service](#)

[Digital Curation Centre](#)

[Digital Research Services](#)

Information for applicants: Please contact UE to find out about their plans for the fellowship.

Contact: Robin Rice, R.Rice@ed.ac.uk

University of Trento (UNITN)

[Research Data Support at UINTN](#)

[UNITN Open Science Policy](#)

Information for applicants: UNITN is developing training material for their researchers on FAIR data, data quality and promotion and valorisation of datasets. Confirmed duration of placement is one month, as approved by the head of the research directorate. Please contact us to find out more.

Contact: Dr Vincenzo Maltese, vincenzo.maltese@unitn.it

List of Host Institutions Contacts for Call 1

Institution	Contact Name	Email Address
4TU.ResearchData	Madeleine de Smaele	M.M.E.deSmaele@tudelft.nl
Aarhus University	Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	bcd@au.dk
Chalmers University of Technology	Jeremy Azzopardi	jeremyaz@chalmers.se
Delft University of Technology	Yan Wang	Y.Wang-16@tudelft.nl
Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change	Fabrizio Antonio	fabrizio.antonio@cmcc.it
Italian Institute of Technology	Valentina Pasquale	Valentina.Pasquale@iit.it
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Claudia Kramer	Sekretariat@bibliothek.kit.edu
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Johan Phillips	johan.philips@kuleuven.be
Polytechnic University of Turin	Mauro Paschetta	mauro.paschetta@polito.it
Technical University of Denmark	Katrine Flindt Holmstrand	kafh@dtu.dk
University of Edinburgh	Robin Rice	R.Rice@ed.ac.uk
University of Trento	Vincenzo Maltese	vincenzo.maltese@unitn.it

Skills4EOSC

Application, budget and CV templates for Skills4EOSC fellowship

Application for SkillsEOSC fellowship programme MO-YYYY	
Personal information	
Applicant name	
ORCID (not mandatory)	
Job title	
Address	
Phone	
E-mail	
Date of birth	
Gender (not mandatory)	
Nationality	
Home institution	
Home institution name	
Home institution ROR if applicable	
Department, Faculty	
Contact person	
E-mail of contact person	
Letter of support from home institution including a statement that salary of applicant is covered by home institution during the fellowship.	<i>Attachment</i>
Mobility rule statement	
Indicate the period(s) and the country/countries in which you have legally resided and/or had your main activity (work, studies etc.) during the last three years up until the application deadline	
Host institution	
Host institution name	

Host institution ROR if applicable	
Host department/ faculty name and address	
Name of contact person	
Job title of contact person	
E-mail of contact person	
Letter of acceptance from host institution	<i>Attachment</i>
Proposal	
Start date of fellowship (YYYY-MO-DD)	
Area of interest	
Detailed plan for fellowship	
A. Plan for the fellow, incl. activities, project, training, seminars etc. (max. 500 words)	
B. Competences/skills to be gained (what the applicant would like to achieve) (max. 250 words)	
C. Reason for choosing the host institution (max. 250 words)	

Budget

Do not include salary of fellow or of any mentors etc. in the budget. Include only costs directly related to the fellowship such as travel, accommodation, insurance, training fees etc. Any costs for the host institution should also be noted in their letter of acceptance.

	Fellowship grant (up to 5000 EUR)	Costs covered by home institution (if applicable)	Costs covered by host institution (if applicable)	Total in EUR
Total in EUR				

Curriculum Vitae of applicant (max. 2 page)
Name of applicant
Education and work/research domain
Highest Degree award date, Name of university, Country
Research field(s), if applicable
Previous position(s)
Years, Position held, Name of University/Institution/Company, Country
Achievements and experience of relevance for fellowship
Professional experience. (max. 200 words)
List of publications, reports, training material, etc. (if any) of relevance for fellowship (max. 5)
Other information of relevance for fellowship
Award(s), Fellowship(s), Scholarship(s) received. Membership in expert groups, scientific advisory board, review board, review panel, editorial board, professional bodies etc.

Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

Call for applications

Introduction

There is increasing need for research-performing organisations to develop and sustain professional profiles related to Open Science, FAIR data and research data management practices. For this reason, the Skills4EOSC Horizon Europe project will sponsor short secondments for (aspiring) data professionals in Open Science (i.e., data stewards and other individuals working in data support relating to Open Science) hereinafter “Fellowship Programme”. Therefore, the Fellowship Programme intends to stimulate life-long learning (knowledge and experience exchange) between data professionals at different institutions and participation to relevant professional networks.

Aim

The aim of the fellowship is to:

- 1) support the life-long learning of data professionals in Open Science by acquiring skills of relevance to Open and FAIR data practices, as well as to research data management practices,
- 2) build or consolidate such practices at institutions,
- 3) acquire knowledge about or establish services, tools and infrastructures of relevance to Open and FAIR data at home institutions,
- 4) strengthen collaboration among institutions, also by fostering participation to relevant professional networks.

The fellowship can take one of three forms:

- **A project proposed by the fellow:** In this scenario, the fellow will bring forth a project that aligns with the objectives and expertise of the host institution. This project could be undertaken within an office or faculty, allowing for a focused and impactful collaboration.
- **Joining a project proposed by the host institution:** Alternatively, the fellow can participate in an existing project proposed by your institution. This option provides an opportunity to leverage the fellow's skills and knowledge to advance ongoing initiatives.
- **An internship in research data support:** The fellow can also engage in an internship, where they will observe and actively participate in day-to-day activities related to research data support. This internship can span across one or multiple offices/departments, offering a comprehensive

understanding of RDM practices within your institution. Whichever of these forms the fellowship takes, it must enhance or benefit the fellow's career and/or their present role.

Duration

The duration of the fellowship can be one, two or three months. The fellow must take up the placement no later than 1 year after being accepted.

Call

Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme Secretariat (hereinafter "Secretariat") will issue two calls for candidates. There will be four places in each call for a total of eight. The first round will open in August 2023, with application deadline on 31st October 2023. The second round will open in December 2023, with deadline on 29th February 2024. Applicants will be notified of decision within two months of deadline.

Application and eligibility

The Fellowship Programme is open to all data professionals in Open Science (data stewards¹ and other individuals working in data support relating to Open Science, or anyone intending to work in this area. Early career professionals are therefore also encouraged to apply.

To be eligible for Skills4EOSC fellowship two conditions apply:

- 1) *Personal eligibility*: Applicants must be affiliated with a publicly funded research-performing organisation in an EU or EU-widening country² and must comply with the mobility rule (see below).
- 2) *Application eligibility*: The applicant must use the provided templates for application, budget and CV. The applicant must adhere to the requirements stated in the templates and include a letter of support from the home institution and a letter or invitation by the host institution.

Host institutions, project description and reporting

In the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme the host institution can be any research-performing organisation within the Skills4EOSC consortium³. The applicant and the host institution must agree on a project, training or internship plan (see above) matching the aims of the Fellowship Programme. The proposed activities and benefits of these must be clearly stated in the application and can be expressed in terms of achieving the fellowship's goals, or new professional skills, e.g. by completing a specific training.

Fellows will commit to participate in a final survey in order to obtain feedback about the fellowship experience, and will be required to write a report, highlighting skills/capabilities gained and suggestions on how to improve the Fellowship Programme (if any). The report will be due no later than one month following the end of the fellowship. Fellows should consider joining a relevant "Data Steward" network, facilitated by the Secretariat, where they can continue to enhance their skills and knowledge, collaborate with other RDM professionals to tackle common challenges, and keep updated with relevant developments.

¹ Please refer to the definition on p. 20 in Jaunsen et al. 2021 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6476940>

² See [Horizon Europe Widening - Who should apply](#)

³ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/about/consortium>

Mobility rule

The mobility rule of this call follows the MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions) mobility rule. The applicants must NOT have resided or carried out their main activities (work, studies etc.) for more than 12 months in the host organization's country in the three years immediately prior to the application deadline. Applicants must indicate the period(s) and the country/countries in which they have legally resided and/or had their main activity (work, studies etc.) during the last three years up until the application deadline.

Eligible costs

Each fellow will receive up to €5.000 to cover travel, accommodation, training costs or any other direct costs related to obtaining outlined skills or goals. Costs for hardware, software or any other equipment are not eligible. The applicant's home institution must agree to cover the salary of the applicant for the whole duration of the fellowship and explicitly state this commitment in the letter of support. The salary of the fellow or of any supervisors /mentors, etc. must not be included in the budget proposal. Additional costs not covered by the fellowship, but covered directly by the applicant or the host institution can be included in the budget proposal if relevant, by using the provided template.

Application package and deadline

The application package consists of the application form, budget proposal and CV. All requested information must be filled out by using the provided templates. No other documents than your CV, letter of support from your home institution and letter of invitation/acceptance from the host institution should be attached.

The application package for the first call must be submitted the latest by 23:59 CET on 31 October 2023.

Evaluation and final selection

The Secretariat consists of Skills4EOSC consortium members. Applications will be assessed by at least two evaluators from the Secretariat. Any evaluators/members of the Secretariat must provide a statement of any conflict of interests concerning the applicant(s) and host institutions within the past 5 years prior to the application deadline and will not express any judgement on applications involving their own institution. Successful applicants will be selected based on evaluators' scores.

Selection criteria

Applications will be evaluated on the basis of the following criteria:

Quality of the applicant (50%)

- Motivation and suitability
- Professional qualifications
- Relevant experience and level of expertise
- Competences/skills to be gained and potential of the applicant to transfer the acquired skills to the home institution

Quality of the fellowship proposal (50%)

- Clear, convincing and compelling goals
- Feasibility: scientific, technological, access to infrastructure, project timeline, associated risks
- Appropriateness of requested resources
- An account of how both the host and the home institutions would have an added value for the fellowship undertaken

Contact

Questions to the call can be addressed to the Secretariat at fellowship@lists.skills4eosc.eu

Link to the Fellowship Programme on Skills4EOSC website:

<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/fellowship-programme>

Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme

Evaluation template

Evaluators remain anonymous to the applicant. Criteria 1 and 2 is evaluated each with a 50% weighting. The evaluators should use the comment section to qualify the final scores.

Name of applicant:

Duration of fellowship:

Criteria	Comments	Score (one digit) 5: Excellent 4: Very good 3: Average 2: Ok 1: Poor
<p>1. Quality of the proposal (max. 2000 characters)</p> <p>Merits and thoroughness of the proposed project: clear, convincing and compelling</p> <p>Feasibility What is the potential for transferring of skills?</p> <p>Appropriateness of requested resources</p> <p>Is it clear why the host institute has an added value for the proposed fellowship?</p>		
<p>2. Quality of the applicant (max. 2000 characters)</p> <p>Professional/academic qualifications and achievements in relation to the stage of career</p> <p>Motivation and suitability</p> <p>Relevant experience and level of expertise</p>		

Appendix A3

Skills to be gained /Potential for home institution		
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Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme - Institution feedback survey

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

This survey about your experience with the Skills4EOSC Fellowship will be part of the report published to finalise the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme.

Mentors at the host institutions are kindly requested to complete it after their experience with fellows has ended. We only ask your name and email to be able to track which Institutions have fulfilled the survey. Data will be deleted when the report of the Fellowship Programme has been published.

We will keep all answers **anonymised**, but we may include paraphrases of your comments in the report.

* Name

* email

* Institution

* How well do you feel your institution/office/project benefited from hosting your fellow? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = not satisfactory; 2 = somewhat satisfactory; 3 = satisfactory; 4 = very satisfactory; 5 = highly satisfactory)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Did any tangible outputs come out of the fellowship?

- Yes
 No

Please select the type of outputs:

- Documents (reports, blogposts, news, guidelines)

- Scientific articles
- Training materials (courses/webinars)
- Processes
- Other

Please link to any of these outputs that are publicly available (DOI, URL, etc.) or make a short description if not openly available:

* In your opinion, how well did the placement benefit the fellow? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = not satisfactory; 2 = somewhat satisfactory; 3 = satisfactory; 4 = very satisfactory; 5 = highly satisfactory)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Were the resources you put into the fellowship worth the outcome?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Are you aware of comparable funding opportunities for data professionals (non-researchers)?

- Yes
- No

If you have answered yes to the previous question, please specify which ones:

* How would you rate the fellowship overall (considering your experience, the benefits, administrative support, etc.)? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = very negative; 2 = negative; 3 = neutral; 4 = positive; 5 = very positive)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

Do you have any comments or suggestions for improvement for future fellowship programmes (for example in terms of duration, costs, invested time, goals, etc.)?

5000 character(s) maximum

Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme - Fellow feedback survey

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

This survey about your experience with the Skills4EOSC Fellowship will be part of the report published to finalise the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme.

All fellows must complete it after their fellowship has ended. We only ask your name and email to be able to track which Fellowship recipients have fulfilled the compulsory survey. Data will be deleted when the report of the Fellowship Programme has been published.

We will keep all answers **anonymised**, but we may include paraphrases of your comments in the report.

* Name

* email

* How long was the total duration of your fellowship (approximately)?

- 1 month
- 2 months
- 3 months

* How do you evaluate the application process? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = very difficult; 2 = difficult; 3 = neutral; 4 = easy; 5 = very easy)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

* How well did the fellowship fulfil the learning and knowledge exchange targets set out in your application proposal? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = not satisfactory; 2 = somewhat satisfactory; 3 = satisfactory; 4 = very satisfactory; 5 = highly satisfactory)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Below are some HARD skills that have been identified as 'essential' for data stewards.

Check the skills you have acquired or improved during your fellowship:

- Knowledge of Open Science practices, policies and regulation and translation of these (when necessary) to local context.
- Service provision to support specific Open Science practices including: applying FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data curation, preservation, archiving and responsible re-use.
- Knowledge about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, intellectual property rights, information security and risk management.
- Awareness raising among data creators, users, and research stakeholders of the value of good data management.
- Provide advice and support on use of infrastructure and tools for data storage, versioning, publishing, and documentation.
- Support Open Science practices, policies and practices through training design and delivery.
- Monitor the research and funding ecosystem, identifying conflicting motivations, drivers and incentives among different stakeholders.
- Knowledge/awareness of programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies.

* Below are some SOFT skills that have been identified as 'essential' for data stewards.

Check the skills you have acquired or improved during your fellowship:

- Conflict management/mediation with a patient, empathic approach.
- Critical and analytical thinking
- Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge their needs.
- Creativity, curiosity, and openness with willingness to learn.
- Team management and project management with results-oriented planning and organising.

If you want to add other skills, please specify which ones:

In your opinion, how essential are these skills for Data Stewards? Please consider either your own role or other people you worked with in the Data steward role, and rate each skills from 1 (not essential) to 5 (essential):

Knowledge of Open Science practices, policies and regulation and translation of these (when necessary) to local context.	
Service provision to support specific Open Science practices including: applying FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data curation, preservation, archiving and responsible re-use.	
Knowledge about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, intellectual property rights, information security and risk management.	

<p>Awareness raising among data creators, users, and research stakeholders of the value of good data management.</p>	
<p>Provide advice and support on use of infrastructure and tools for data storage, versioning, publishing, and documentation.</p>	
<p>Support Open Science practices, policies and practices through training design and delivery.</p>	
<p>Monitor the research and funding ecosystem, identifying conflicting motivations, drivers and incentives among different stakeholders.</p>	
<p>Knowledge/awareness of programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies.</p>	
<p>Conflict management/mediation with a patient, empathic approach.</p>	
<p>Critical and analytical thinking</p>	
<p>Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge their needs.</p>	
<p>Creativity, curiosity, and openness with willingness to learn.</p>	
<p>Team management and project management with results-oriented planning and organising.</p>	

* Will the fellowship enable you to pursue new career paths or make a step forward in your career?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Did any tangible outputs come out of the fellowship?

- Yes
- No

Please link to any of these outputs that are publicly available (DOI, URL, etc.) or make a short description if not openly available:

* How well did the experience at your host institution meet your expectations? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = not satisfactory; 2 = somewhat satisfactory; 3 = satisfactory; 4 = very satisfactory; 5 = highly satisfactory)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

* Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

* Are you aware of comparable funding opportunities for data professionals (non-researchers)?

- Yes
- No

If you have answered yes to the previous question, please specify which ones:

* Are you part of an existing RDM/Open Science/FAIR/data steward network or community?

- Yes
- No

* Please elaborate your answer to the previous question (if you answered "yes", please specify which groups or communities you are in; if "no", please say if you would be interested to join a group):

* How would you rate the fellowship overall (considering your experience, the benefits, administrative support, etc.)? (Please use integers in your answer. Legend: 1 = very negative; 2 = negative; 3 = neutral; 4 = positive; 5 = very positive)

Only values between 1 and 5 are allowed

Do you have any additional comments?

5000 character(s) maximum

Skills4EOSC Fellowship Award Certificate

Fellow's Name, Fellow's role and department at home institution, Home Institution Name, Country, was awarded a grant by the Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme in December 2023.

The aim of the Fellowship Programme is to support life-long learning for data professionals in Open Science and to stimulate professional growth in Open and FAIR data practices and research data management.

Duration of fellowship: Start date – finishing date

Fellowship host: Name, role and department of mentor at host institution, Name of host institution, Country

On behalf of the Fellowship Programme,

Signature of WP6 Lead

Curtis Sharma